

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

Bibliography of KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module B: AI, trust and awareness

D3.1 MOD. B

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Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module B focuses on the risks AI poses for social fairness and trust: how the use of AI-based tools can generate inequality or dishonesty, particularly when human productions differ in nature (e.g. creative vs. repetitive tasks), and how such dynamics impact trust between individuals and institutions.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

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Bibliography of KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module B: AI, trust and awareness

- Acerbi, A. (2019a). Cognitive attraction and online misinformation. *Palgrave Communications*, 5(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0224-y>
- Acerbi, A. (2019b). *Cultural Evolution in the Digital Age*. Oxford University Press.
- Acikgoz, Y. (2019). Employee recruitment and job search: Towards a multi-level integration. *Human Resource Management Review*, 29(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2018.02.009>
- Acikgoz, Y., Davison, K. H., Compagnone, M., & Laske, M. (2020). Justice perceptions of artificial intelligence in selection. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 28(4), 399-416. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijsa.12306>
- Agudo, U., Arrese, M., Liberal, K. G., & Matute, H. (2022). Assessing Emotion and Sensitivity of AI Artwork. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 879088. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.879088>
- Allen, J., Watts, D. J., & Rand, D. G. (2024). Quantifying the impact of misinformation and vaccine-skeptical content on Facebook. *Science*, 384(6699), eadk3451. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adk3451>
- Altay, S., Berriche, M., & Acerbi, A. (2023). Misinformation on Misinformation: Conceptual and Methodological Challenges. *Social Media + Society*, 9(1), 20563051221150412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051221150412>
- Anantrasirichai, N., & Bull, D. (2022). Artificial intelligence in the creative industries: a review. *Artificial intelligence review* 55, 589–656.
- Bail, C. A., Argyle, L. P., Brown, T. W., Bumpus, J. P., Chen, H., Hunzaker, M. B. F., Lee, J., Mann, M., Merhout, F., & Volfovsky, A. (2018). Exposure to opposing views on social media can increase political polarization. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(37), 9216-9221. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1804840115>
- Bajwa, J., Munir, U., Nori, A., & Williams, B. (2021). Artificial intelligence in healthcare: Transforming the practice of medicine. *Future Healthcare Journal*, 8(2), e188–e194. <https://doi.org/10.7861/fhj.2021-0095>
- Bakshy, E., Messing, S., & Adamic, L. A. (2015). Exposure to ideologically diverse news and opinion on Facebook. *Science*, 348(6239), 1130-1132. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa1160>
- Bankins, S., & Formosa, P. (2023). The Ethical Implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) For Meaningful Work. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 185(4), 725-740.
- Bankins, S., Formosa, P., Griep, Y., & Richards, D. (2022). AI Decision Making with Dignity? Contrasting Workers' Justice Perceptions of Human and AI Decision Making in a Human Resource Management Context. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 24(3), 857-875. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-021-10223-8>
- Bates, D., Maechler, M., Bolker, B., Walker, S., Christensen, R.H.B., Singmann, H., Dai, B., Grothendieck, G., Green, P. & Bolker, M.B. (2015). Package 'lme4'. *Convergence* 12.
- Baumard, N. (2011). Punishment is not a group adaptation : Humans punish to restore fairness rather than to support group cooperation. *Mind & Society*, 10(1).<https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:7a8e4dee-109a-4abd-a16d-367fc33512d1>

- Baumard, N., André, J.-B., & Sperber, D. (2013). A mutualistic approach to morality: The evolution of fairness by partner choice. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 36(1), 59-78. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X11002202>
- Beasley, E. M. (2014). Students Reported for Cheating Explain What They Think Would Have Stopped Them. *Ethics & Behavior*, 24(3), 229-252. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2013.845533>
- Bellaiche, L., Shahi, R., Turpin, M. H., Ragnhildstveit, A., Sprockett, S., Barr, N., Christensen, A., & Seli, P. (2023). Humans versus AI: Whether and why we prefer human-created compared to AI-created artwork. *Cognitive Research: Principles and Implications*, 8, 42. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41235-023-00499-6>
- Bender, E. M., Gebru, T., McMillan-Major, A., & Shmitchell, S. (2021). On the Dangers of Stochastic Parrots: Can Language Models Be Too Big? 🦜. *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 610-623. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442188.3445922>
- Benkler, Y., Faris, R., Roberts, H., Benkler, Y., Faris, R., & Roberts, H. (2018). *Network Propaganda: Manipulation, Disinformation, and Radicalization in American Politics*. Oxford University Press.
- Black, J. S., & van Esch, P. (2020). AI-enabled recruiting: What is it and how should a manager use it? *Business Horizons*, 63(2), 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2019.12.001>
- Blaine, T., & Boyer, P. (2018). Origins of sinister rumors: A preference for threat-related material in the supply and demand of information. *Evolution and Human Behavior*, 39(1), 67-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2017.10.001>
- Bor, A., & Petersen, M. B. (2022). The Psychology of Online Political Hostility: A Comprehensive, Cross-National Test of the Mismatch Hypothesis. *American Political Science Review*, 116(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055421000885>
- Bouchaud, P., Chavalarias, D., & Panahi, M. (2023). Crowdsourced audit of Twitter's recommender systems. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 16815. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-43980-4>
- Boyer, P., & Parren, N. (2015). Threat-Related Information Suggests Competence: A Possible Factor in the Spread of Rumors. *PLOS ONE*, 10(6), e0128421. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0128421>
- Brady, W. J., Wills, J. A., Jost, J. T., Tucker, J. A., & Van Bavel, J. J. (2017). Emotion shapes the diffusion of moralized content in social networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(28), 7313-7318. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1618923114>
- Broadbent, S., Forestier, F., Khamassi, M., & Zolynski, C. (2024). *Pour une nouvelle culture de l'attention: Que faire de ces réseaux sociaux qui nous épuisent?* Odile Jacob.
- Castelo, N., Bos, M. W., & Lehmann, D. R. (2019). Task-Dependent Algorithm Aversion. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 56(5), 809-825.
- Cetinic, E., & She, J. (2022). Understanding and creating art with ai: Review and outlook. *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications* 18, 66:1–66:22. [doi:10.1145/3475799](https://doi.org/10.1145/3475799).
- Ch'ng, E. (2019). Art by computing machinery: Is machine art acceptable in the artworld? *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications* 15, 59:1–59:17. [doi:10.1145/3326338](https://doi.org/10.1145/3326338).

- Chamberlain, R., Mullin, C., Scheerlinck, & B., Wagemans, J. (2017). Putting the art in artificial: Aesthetic responses to computer-generated art. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts* 12. doi:10.1037/aca0000136.
- Chavalarias, D. (2023). *Toxic Data*. Flammarion.
- Clark, C. J., Liu, B. S., Winegard, B. M., & Ditto, P. H. (2019). Tribalism Is Human Nature. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 28(6), 587-592. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721419862289>
- Cohen, J. (2013). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. Routledge.
- Coleman, E. B. (2001). Aboriginal Painting : Identity and Authenticity. *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism*, 59(4), 385-402.
- Combs, A., Tierney, G., Guay, B., Merhout, F., Bail, C. A., Hillygus, D. S., & Volfovsky, A. (2023). Reducing political polarization in the United States with a mobile chat platform. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 7(9), 1454-1461. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-023-01655-0>
- Csibra, G., & Gergely, G. (2009). Natural pedagogy. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 13(4), 148-153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2009.01.005>
- Dastin, J. (2018). Insight - Amazon scraps secret AI recruiting tool that showed bias against women. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/article/world/insight-amazon-scraps-secret-ai-recruiting-tool-that-showed-bias-against-women-idUSKCN1MK0AG/>
- De Francisci Morales, G., Monti, C., & Starnini, M. (2021). No echo in the chambers of political interactions on Reddit. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 2818. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-81531-x>
- Debove, S., Baumard, N., & André, J.-B. (2017). On the evolutionary origins of equity. *PLOS ONE*, 12(3), e0173636. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0173636>
- Di Dio, C., Ardizzi, M., Schieppati, S. V., Massaro, D., Gilli, G., Gallese, V., & Marchetti, A. (2023). Art made by artificial intelligence : The effect of authorship on aesthetic judgments. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, No Pagination Specified-No Pagination Specified. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000602>
- Dobber, T., Metoui, N., Trilling, D., Helberger, N., & De Vreese, C. (2021). Do (Microtargeted) Deepfakes Have Real Effects on Political Attitudes? *The International Journal of Press/Politics*, 26(1), 69-91. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1940161220944364>
- Druckman, J. N. (2022). A Framework for the Study of Persuasion. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 25(Volume 25, 2022), 65-88. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-051120-110428>
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Hughes, L., Ismagilova, E., Aarts, G., Coombs, C., Crick, T., Duan, Y., Dwivedi, R., Edwards, J., Eirug, A., Galanos, V., Ilavarasan, P. V., Janssen, M., Jones, P., Kar, A. K., Kizgin, H., Kronemann, B., Lal, B., Lucini, B., ... Williams, M. D. (2021). Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice and policy. *International Journal of Information Management*, 57, 101994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.08.002>
- Eke, D. O. (2023). ChatGPT and the rise of generative AI : Threat to academic integrity? *Journal of Responsible Technology*, 13, 100060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrt.2023.100060>
- Etienne, H. (2021). The future of online trust (and why Deepfake is advancing it). *AI and Ethics*, 1(4), 553-562. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-021-00072-1>

- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Lang, A.-G., & Buchner, A. (2007). G*Power 3 : A flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behavior Research Methods*, 39(2), 175-191. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193146>
- Figueroa-Armijos, M., Clark, B., & Veiga, S. da M. (2022). Ethical Perceptions of AI in Hiring and Organizational Trust: The Role of Performance Expectancy and Social Influence. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 186, 179–197.
- Fraij, J., & László, V. (2021). A Literature Review: Artificial Intelligence Impact on the Recruitment Process. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Sciences*, 6(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.21791/IJEMS.2021.1.10>
- Fuchs, C., Schreier, M., & van Osselaer, S. M. J. (2015). The handmade effect : What’s love got to do with it? *Journal of Marketing*, 79(2), 98-110. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jm.14.0018>
- Gallotti, M., & Frith, C. D. (2013). Social cognition in the we-mode. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 17(4), 160-165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2013.02.002>
- Grassini, S., & Koivisto, M. (2024). Understanding how personality traits, experiences, and attitudes shape negative bias toward ai-generated artworks. *Scientific Reports* 14, 4113. doi:10.1038/s41598-024-54294-4.
- Grinberg, N., Joseph, K., Friedland, L., Swire-Thompson, B., & Lazer, D. (2019). Fake news on Twitter during the 2016 U.S. presidential election. *Science*, 363(6425), 374-378. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aau2706>
- Grubbs, J. B., Warmke, B., Tosi, J., James, A. S., & Campbell, W. K. (2019). Moral grandstanding in public discourse : Status-seeking motives as a potential explanatory mechanism in predicting conflict. *PLOS ONE*, 14(10), e0223749. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0223749>
- Guess, A., Lyons, B., Nyhan, B., & Reifler, J. (2018). *Avoiding the echo chamber about echo chambers : Why selective exposure to like-minded political news is less prevalent than you think.*
- Gunser, V. E., Gottschling, S., Brucker, B., Richter, S., Çakir, D. C., & Gerjets, P. (2022). The Pure Poet : How Good is the Subjective Credibility and Stylistic Quality of Literary Short Texts Written with an Artificial Intelligence Tool as Compared to Texts Written by Human Authors? In T.-H. « Kenneth » Huang, V. Raheja, D. Kang, J. J. Y. Chung, D. Gissin, M. Lee, & K. I. Gero (Éds.), *Proceedings of the First Workshop on Intelligent and Interactive Writing Assistants (In2Writing 2022)* (p. 60-61). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.in2writing-1.8>
- Homans, G. C. (1958). Social Behavior as Exchange. *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), 597-606.
- Horodyski, P. (2023). Applicants’ perception of artificial intelligence in the recruitment process. *Computers in Human Behavior Reports*, 11, 100303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2023.100303>
- Horton Jr, C. B., White, M. W., & Iyengar, S. S. (2023). Bias against AI art can enhance perceptions of human creativity. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 19001. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-45202-3>
- Horton, C.B., White, M.W., & Iyengar, S.S. (2023). Bias against ai art can enhance perceptions of human creativity. *Scientific Reports* 13, 19001. doi:10.1038/s41598-023-45202-3.
- Hu, S., Ke, F., Vyortkina, D., Hu, P., Luby, S., & O’Shea, J. (2025). Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: Applications, Challenges, and Policy Development and Further Considerations. In *Higher Education: Handbook of Theory and Research* (pp. 1–52). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-51930-7_13-1

- Hunkenschroer, A. L., & Luetge, C. (2022). Ethics of AI-Enabled Recruiting and Selection : A Review and Research Agenda. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 178(4), 977-1007. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-05049-6>
- Ivcevic, Z., Grandinetti, M., 2024. Artificial intelligence as a tool for creativity. *Journal of Creativity* 34, 100079. doi:10.1016/j.yjoc.2024.100079.
- Jakesch, M., Hancock, J. T., & Naaman, M. (2023). Human heuristics for AI-generated language are flawed. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(11), e2208839120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2208839120>
- Judge, M., Fernando, J. W., Paladino, A., & Kashima, Y. (2020). Folk theories of artifact creation : How intuitions about human labor influence the value of artifacts. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 24(3), 195-211. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868320905763>
- Kirk, C. P., & Givi, J. (2025). The AI-authorship effect: Understanding authenticity, moral disgust, and consumer responses to AI-generated marketing communications. *Journal of Business Research*, 186, 114984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2024.114984>
- Köchling, A., Wehner, M. C., & Warkocz, J. (2023). Can I show my skills? Affective responses to artificial intelligence in the recruitment process. *Review of Managerial Science*, 17(6), 2109-2138. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00514-4>
- Kosinski, M. (2021). Facial recognition technology can expose political orientation from naturalistic facial images. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 100. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-79310-1>
- Kramer, A. D. I., Guillory, J. E., & Hancock, J. T. (2014). Experimental evidence of massive-scale emotional contagion through social networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(24), 8788-8790. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1320040111>
- Kruger, J., Wirtz, D., Van Boven, L., & Altermatt, T. W. (2004). The effort heuristic. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 40(1), 91-98. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1031\(03\)00065-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1031(03)00065-9)
- Kunda, Z. (1990). The case for motivated reasoning. *Psychological bulletin*, 108(3), 480.
- Langer, M., König, C. J., Back, C., & Hemsing, V. (2022). Trust in artificial intelligence : Comparing trust processes between human and automated trustees in light of unfair bias. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, No Pagination Specified-No Pagination Specified. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-022-09829-9>
- Lavanchy, M., Reichert, P., Narayanan, J., & Savani, K. (2023). Applicants' Fairness Perceptions of Algorithm-Driven Hiring Procedures. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 188(1), 125-150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-05320-w>
- Lee, M. K. (2018). Understanding perception of algorithmic decisions : Fairness, trust, and emotion in response to algorithmic management. *Big Data & Society*, 5(1), 2053951718756684. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951718756684>
- Lee, M. K. (2018). Understanding perception of algorithmic decisions: Fairness, trust, and emotion in response to algorithmic management. *Big Data & Society*, 5(1), 2053951718756684. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951718756684>
- Lehmann, E. L., & D'Abrera, H. J. M. (1998). *Nonparametrics : Statistical Methods Based on Ranks*. Prentice Hall.

- Lewandowsky, S., Ecker, U. K. H., Cook, J., van der Linden, S., Roozenbeek, J., & Oreskes, N. (2023). Misinformation and the epistemic integrity of democracy. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 54, 101711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2023.101711>
- Lewandowsky, S., Robertson, R. E., & DiResta, R. (2024). Challenges in Understanding Human-Algorithm Entanglement During Online Information Consumption. *Perspectives on Psychological Science: A Journal of the Association for Psychological Science*, 19(5), 758-766. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17456916231180809>
- Lubart, T., & Thornhill-Miller, B. (2020). Creativity: An overview of the 7c's of creative thought, in: *Creativity and Innovation*, pp. 277–305. doi:10.17885/heiup.470.c6678.
- Magni, F., Park, J., & Chao, M. M. (2024). Humans as Creativity Gatekeepers : Are We Biased Against AI Creativity? *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 39(3), 643-656. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-023-09910-x>
- Magni, F., Park, J., & Chao, M.M. (2024). Humans as creativity gatekeepers: Are we biased against ai creativity? *Journal of Business and Psychology* 39, 643–656. doi:10.1007/s10869-023-09910-x.
- Malle, B. F. (2021). Moral judgments. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 72, 293-318. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-072220-104358>
- Marie, A., Altay, S., & Strickland, B. (2020). The cognitive foundations of misinformation on science : What we know and what scientists can do about it. *EMBO Reports*, 21(4), e50205. <https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.202050205>
- Martel, C., Allen, J., Pennycook, G., & Rand, D. G. (2024). Crowds Can Effectively Identify Misinformation at Scale. *Perspectives on Psychological Science: A Journal of the Association for Psychological Science*, 19(2), 477-488. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17456916231190388>
- McCallum, K., Mitchell, S., Scott-Phillips, T. (2020). The art experience. *Review of philosophy and psychology* 11, 21–35.
- McCarthy, J. M., Bauer, T. N., Truxillo, D. M., Anderson, N. R., Costa, A. C., & Ahmed, S. M. (2017). Applicant Perspectives During Selection: A Review Addressing “So What?,” “What’s New?,” and “Where to Next?” *Journal of Management*, 43(6), 1693–1725. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206316681846>
- Mori, M., Sasseti, S., Cavaliere, V., Bonti, M. (2025). A systematic literature review on artificial intelligence in recruiting and selection: a matter of ethics. *Personnel Review* 54, 854–878.
- Moruzzi, C. (2022). Creative agents: Rethinking agency and creativity in human and artificial systems. *Journal of Aesthetics and Phenomenology* 9, 245–268. doi:10.1080/20539320.2022.2150470.
- Moruzzi, C. (2025). Artificial intelligence and creativity. *Philosophy Compass* 20, e70030. doi:10.1111/phc3.70030.
- Newman, D., Nathanael J. Fast, & Harmon, D. J. (2020). When eliminating bias isn't fair : Algorithmic reductionism and procedural justice in human resource decisions. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 160, 149-167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2020.03.008>
- Newman, G. E., & Bloom, P. (2012). Art and authenticity : The importance of originals in judgments of value. *Journal of Experimental Psychology. General*, 141(3), 558-569. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0026035>
- Nguyen, T., & Elbanna, A. (2025). Understanding Human-AI Augmentation in the Workplace: A Review and a Future Research Agenda. *Information Systems Frontiers*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-025-10591-5>

- Noble, S. M., Foster, L. L., & Craig, S. B. (2021). The procedural and interpersonal justice of automated application and resume screening. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 29(2), 139-153. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijsa.12320>
- Origgi, G., Holmes, S., & Arikha, N. (2018). *Reputation : What It Is and Why It Matters*. Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvc77bzk>
- Oswald, L., Schulz, W. S., & Lorenz-Spreen, P. (2025). Disentangling participation in online political discussions with a collective field experiment. *Science Advances*, 11(50), eady8022.
- Pan, Y., Froese, F., Liu, N., Yunyang, H., & Ye, M. (2021). The adoption of artificial intelligence in employee recruitment: The influence of contextual factors. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 33, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2021.1879206>
- Perera, V. (2024). *Applications of AI in Talent Acquisition and Recruitment*. Conference: 8th CIPM International Research SymposiumAt: Colombo, Sri Lanka.
- Preiksaitis, C., Nash, C., Gottlieb, M., Chan, T. M., Alvarez, A., & Landry, A. (2023). Brain versus bot : Distinguishing letters of recommendation authored by humans compared with artificial intelligence. *AEM Education and Training*, 7(6), 10.1002/aet.2.10924. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aet.2.10924>
- Ragot, M., Martin, N., & Cojean, S. (2020). AI-generated vs. Human Artworks. A Perception Bias Towards Artificial Intelligence? *Extended Abstracts of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3334480.3382892>
- Rahwan, I., Cebrian, M., Obradovich, N., Bongard, J., Bonnefon, J.F., Breazeal, C., Crandall, J.W., Christakis, N.A., Couzin, I.D., Jackson, M.O., Jennings, N.R., Kamar, E., Kloumann, I.M., Larochelle, H., Lazer, D., McElreath, R., Mislove, A., Parkes, D.C., Pentland, A.S., & Wellman, M. (2019). Machine behaviour. *Nature* 568, 477–486. doi:10.1038/s41586-019-1138-y.
- Rasmussen, S. H. R., Ludeke, S. G., & Klemmensen, R. (2023). Using deep learning to predict ideology from facial photographs : Expressions, beauty, and extra-facial information. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 5257. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31796-1>
- Rathje, S., Van Bavel, J. J., & van der Linden, S. (2021). Out-group animosity drives engagement on social media. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(26), e2024292118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2024292118>
- Reich, R. (2022). Now AI can write students' essays for them, will everyone become a cheat? *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2022/nov/28/ai-students-essays-cheat-teachers-plagiarism-tech>.
- Rigotti, C., & Fosch-Villaronga, E. (2024). Fairness, AI & recruitment. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 53, 105966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2024.105966>
- Runco, M. A. (2023). AI can only produce artificial creativity. *Journal of Creativity*, 33(3), 100063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yjoc.2023.100063>
- Runco, M.A., 2023. Ai can only produce artificial creativity. *Journal of Creativity* 33, 100063. doi:10.1016/j.yjoc.2023.100063.
- Santos, F. P., Lelkes, Y., & Levin, S. A. (2021). Link recommendation algorithms and dynamics of polarization in online social networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(50), e2102141118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2102141118>

- Schaffner, B. F., & Luks, S. (2018). Misinformation or Expressive Responding? What an Inauguration Crowd Can Tell Us about the source of Political Misinformation in Surveys. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 82(1), 135-147. <https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfx042>
- Schilke, O., Reimann, M. (2025). The transparency dilemma: How ai disclosure erodes trust. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 188, 104405.
- Shaheen, M. Y. (2021). *Applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in healthcare: A review*. <https://doi.org/10.17613/gcz6-1487>
- Shank, D. B., Stefanik, C., Stuhlsatz, C., Kacirek, K., & Belfi, A. M. (2023). AI composer bias : Listeners like music less when they think it was composed by an AI. *Journal of Experimental Psychology. Applied*, 29(3), 676-692. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xap0000447>
- Shteynberg, G., Hirsh, J. B., Bentley, R. A., & Garthoff, J. (2020). Shared worlds and shared minds : A theory of collective learning and a psychology of common knowledge. *Psychological Review*, 127(5), 918-931. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000200>
- Skitka, L. J., & Wisneski, D. C. (2013). Justice theory and research : A social functionalist perspective. In *Handbook of psychology : Personality and social psychology, Vol. 5, 2nd ed* (p. 407-427). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Sperber, D., Wilson, D. (1995). *Relevance: Communication and Cognition*. 2nd ed., Blackwell, Oxford, UK.
- Stone, D. L., Lukaszewski, K. M., Stone-Romero, E. F., & Johnson, T. L. (2013). Factors affecting the effectiveness and acceptance of electronic selection systems. *Human Resource Management Review*, 23(1), 50–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2012.06.006>
- Straub, V. J., Hashem, Y., Bright, J., Bhagwanani, S., Morgan, D., Francis, J., Esnaashari, S., & Margetts, H. (2024). *AI for bureaucratic productivity: Measuring the potential of AI to help automate 143 million UK government transactions*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2403.14712>
- Sweeney, S. (2023). Who wrote this? Essay mills and assessment – Considerations regarding contract cheating and AI in higher education. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 21(2), 100818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100818>
- Taber, C. S., & Lodge, M. (2006). Motivated skepticism in the evaluation of political beliefs. *American journal of political science*, 50(3), 755-769.
- Tambe, P., Cappelli, P., & Yakubovich, V. (2019). Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources Management: Challenges and a Path Forward. *California Management Review*, 61(4), 15–42. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125619867910>
- Tao, R., Su, C.-W., Xiao, Y., Dai, K., & Khalid, F. (2021). Robo advisors, algorithmic trading and investment management: Wonders of fourth industrial revolution in financial markets. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 163(C). <https://ideas.repec.org/a/eee/tefoso/v163y2021ics0040162520312476.html>
- Thébaud, C., Dupont, J.-C. K., Jolivet, V., & Scemama, O. (2023). Évaluer individuellement l'efficacité et l'efficience attendue des thérapeutiques dans l'aide à la décision médicale grâce à l'intelligence artificielle (IA) : Quels enjeux éthiques ? *Éthique publique. Revue internationale d'éthique sociétale et gouvernementale, vol. 25, n° 1*, Article 25, n° 1. <https://doi.org/10.4000/ethiquepublique.7984>
- Tigre Moura, F., & Maw, C. (2021). Artificial intelligence became Beethoven: How do listeners and music professionals perceive artificially composed music? *Journal of Consumer Marketing, ahead-of-print*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-02-2020-3671>

- Tomasello, M., Carpenter, M., Call, J., Behne, T., & Moll, H. (2005). Understanding and sharing intentions : The origins of cultural cognition. *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 28(5), 675-691; discussion 691-735. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X05000129>
- Törnberg, P. (2022). How digital media drive affective polarization through partisan sorting. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(42), e2207159119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2207159119>
- Treullier, C., Castagnos, S., Lagier, C., & Brun, A. (2024). Gaining a better understanding of online polarization by approaching it as a dynamic process. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 8702.
- Upadhyay, A. K., & Khandelwal, K. (2018). Applying artificial intelligence: Implications for recruitment. *Strategic HR Review*, 17(5), 255–258. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SHR-07-2018-0051>
- Van Bavel, J. J., & Pereira, A. (2018). The Partisan Brain : An Identity-Based Model of Political Belief. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 22(3), 213-224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2018.01.004>
- Van Bijnen, E., & Greco, S. (2018). Divide to unite: Making disagreement explicit in dispute mediation. *Journal of argumentation in context*, 7(3), 285-315.
- van Esch, P., Black, J. S., & Ferolie, J. (2019). Marketing AI recruitment: The next phase in job application and selection. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 90, 215–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.09.009>
- Varma, A., Dawkins, C., & Chaudhuri, K. (2023). Artificial intelligence and people management: A critical assessment through the ethical lens. *Human Resource Management Review*, 33(1), 100923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2022.100923>
- Vedapradha, R., Ravi, H., & Rajan, S. (2019). Artificial Intelligence: A Technological Prototype in Recruitment. *Journal of Service Science and Management*, 12, 382–390. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jssm.2019.123026>
- Vosoughi, S., Roy, D., & Aral, S. (2018). The spread of true and false news online. *Science*, 359(6380), 1146-1151. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap9559>
- Vuković, D. B., Dekpo-Adza, S., & Matović, S. (2025). AI integration in financial services: A systematic review of trends and regulatory challenges. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-04850-8>
- Walker, H. J., Helmuth, C. A., Feild, H. S., & Bauer, T. N. (2015). Watch What You Say: Job Applicants' Justice Perceptions From Initial Organizational Correspondence. *Human Resource Management*, 54(6), 999–1011. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21655>
- Wilson, D., Sperber, D. (2004). Relevance theory, in: Horn, L.R., Ward, G. (Eds.), *The Handbook of Pragmatics*. Blackwell, Oxford, UK, pp. 607–632.
- Woods, S. A., Ahmed, S., Nikolaou, I., Costa, A. C., & Anderson, N. R. (2020). Personnel selection in the digital age: A review of validity and applicant reactions, and future research challenges. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 29(1), 64–77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2019.1681401>
- Zabelina, D.L., Robinson, M.D. (2010). Creativity as flexible cognitive control. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts* 4, 136–143. doi:10.1037/a0017379.

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